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Negotiating History: Re-presentation of Women in Colonial Assam

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Abstract:

The main objective of this paper is to examine the agency and resistance of women in colonial Assam. This calls for an understanding of the social engagement of the texts studied and how they reflect and constitute culture. Further, it would demonstrate how women participated in the crucial social and political questions of colonial Assam as recorded in the journals published during that time. These journals provide us an insight into the contemporary attitude of the colonized in Assam which need to be deliberated upon in order to understand the status of the colonial women. The dire need and struggles for emancipation of women can be traced in these writings; the intelligentsia of colonial Assam had mixed feelings, but the fact that women took to writing is a proof enough of their repressed desires for equality. Their self-assertion in carving an identity for themselves and thereby establishing their inherent position in history is to be explored. Re-presentation of these remarkable Assamese women in colonial times is itself a new way of negotiating history to establish their significance in present times. Negotiation of history through re-presentation calls for an exploration of lived experiences and the thrust would go to life stories of such historical women personalities of colonial Assam that are no less exciting than fictional characters. Such explorations seek to establish that contemporary authors like Tilottama Misra, Mamoni Roisom Goswami, Nirupama Borgohain and Anuradha Sarma Pujari, have made significant exploration of colonial Assamese women as transmitters of culture and bearers of change, thus offering an alternative perspective that challenges the traditional views of women's role and agency.

Keywords: Re-presentation, Colonial Woman, Agency.

Assam in the nineteenth century saw the advent of the American Baptist Missionaries before the British came in. They brought along with them the printing machine that saw the publication of the first periodical, *Orunodoi*, in Assamese in 1846. Dealing extensively with

women's issues along with other articles the pages of the journal today are an important source for history of the nineteenth century. It carries the call for social reforms made by the missionaries, and through its pages we come to know of the lone case of attempted *sati* in Assam. This is the only and the first recorded case that took place in Kalugaon in Sibsagar. As recorded, the widow of the elder brother of Lambodar Mauzadar was ready to be a *sati* at the death of her husband, but it was averted in time by the then *daroga* (SL. NO XVII). *Orunodoi* also saw the publication of articles on widow remarriage, supposed to be written by Gunabhiram Barua whose *Ramnavami Natak* was also serialized in fifteen issues of the periodical in 1858. *Ramnavami* is considered to be the first Assamese social drama that upheld widow remarriage.

It was also because of the efforts of American Baptist Missionaries that the issue of women's education gained momentum during this period. The Missionaries, especially the Missionary wives, worked zealously for the education of the girls. Schools were set up, but had to face a lot of opposition and criticism from the society. The *Orunodoi* speaks of the kind of attitude the Assamese people had on hearing about women's education. In *Orunodoi* the writer states that "the main barriers to women's education were the women's own belief, imposed upon them from birth, in their ignorance and inability to learn; and the ridicule they faced if they ever tried to do so." Their objective in educating the girls was to enable them to read the Bible and the scriptures in their own language as translated by the missionaries themselves. Such "plain education" along with sewing and weaving were considered sufficient for the girls to qualify them to become the "meet companions" of the native brethren. But they failed in reaching out to the women of the Assamese upper classes as remarked by Orel Keler in 1886: "We could only gain access to many of the higher castes by teaching some kind of needle work. Now we are usually made welcome and get a hearing, most opposition from higher castes, Brahmins, Mussalmans, though there!" (Barpujari202)

The debate on women's education in Assam took place mainly in the pages of *Assam Bandhu* (1885-86), *Mou* (1886-87) and *Jonaki* (1889-1906). *Assam Bandhu* in its short span of sixteen years published many writings on women's education that includes two contributions by women writers – one by Padmawati Devi Phukanani and the other by Swarnalata. In spite of their feeble voices, it is significant that they were the voices of women who were never expected to speak their views. In contrast to them the opposing voices of Ratneswar Mahanta, Purnakanta Sharma and Lambodar Bora in the pages of *Assam Bandhu* were very strong and they vehemently opposed women's education. In their own different ways, they all saw women's education as a threat to the sanctity of Assamese society. The fear loomed large in

their writings that the spread of western ideas in regard to women's education would take its toll on the female moral character. Mahanta and Sharma were of the view that if women were educated, they would not only avoid the household chores, but would also neglect their wifely duties and head for a moral degradation. They held the view that while boys could be trusted with the *bot-tala* (Jnanadharam Barua 380) books, girls were not to be trusted being weaker in minds. Lamboodar Bora in his satirical dictionary gives a definition of "*stri-swadhinata*" (woman's independence) as a woman who rides on the male by stepping on him (24). He also gives a meaning of "*Bharjya*" as a woman who shows off her husband's wealth (25).

In contrast to such degrading comments, the writings by Padmawati Devi Phukanani and Swarnalata come as a whiff of fresh air with endearing views regarding a woman's individual self. In her "*Narir Muktabastha*" (Women's Free State), Phukanani extols the dexterity of ancient Aryan women like Chitrlekha who upheld their right to freedom (226). Swarnalata too, in spite of being a mere schoolgirl, is able to air her view regarding the purdah system prevailing at that time in her "*Prakrita Laaj Ki?*" (What is True Shame?) (537). Her technique of driving home the point by using dialogues between two girls is engrossing and thought-provoking. In the article the two girls come to the point that the sense of shame does not depend on the veil or purdah, but depends on the state of the mind, whether the thoughts are pure or impure. This is also evident of the young writer's awareness of the need for women's education.

Soon after, another periodical *Mou* (1886) was published which too did not survive for long. In spite of the four published issues only, the periodical provides a definite male-centric view regarding women's education. The stance taken by its editor Bolinarayan Bora, authoring most of the articles, comes as a surprise because he was educated abroad and had an educated wife who moved freely in the social circles. Bora saw women's education as more dangerous than the Burmese invasion and saw women becoming doctors or lawyers as a transgression of gender roles thereby losing their feminine character. He preferred girls to be imparted the rudiments of education at home in order to make them efficient in the affairs of the home.

The periodical *Jonaki* (1889) followed with the tune a bit changed. Now the debate went on as to have the women educated in order to procure a companionate wife who would be a good listener of the husband's intellectual pursuits. It is best echoed in what Phanindranath Gogoi had to say in the pages of *Jonaki* – "While I am in favour of women's education, I do not support the present system. I am totally against a type of education for women that would enable them to pass their B.A or M. A. examinations, and encourage them to compete with their husbands. I do not see the necessity for a woman to be educated like a man, since such

education causes more harm than good” (Mahanta³²). Women’s education was accepted as a medium to produce educated children who would become the future leaders of the country. Queen Victoria was presented as the role model for being a queen in spite of the absence of her father: it was because of her educated mother that she was able to sit on the throne and reign.

After *Jonaki* ceased to publish, other publications came into being like *Usha* (1906), *Alochani* (1909) and *Banhi* (1909). They too carried on the debate regarding the contemporary social issues and saw an increasing number of women contributors. The common theme that ran through them was a support for women’s education that would make them more compatible to the inner confines of the home and not to the outer world. It has to be noted that it was the voice of a woman, Dr. Durgabashini Das, who pointed out clearly in *Alochani* that women need to be educated for the welfare of the country. She made a direct appeal to the educated that instead of doing all the talking they should be resolute to spread women’s education. It is also surprising that Lakshminath Bezbarua, who was one of those who vehemently protested against Bolinarayan Bora’s *Mou* and was all praise for the progress women showed in Dibrugarh and Golaghat, too called for an education that would enable women to be the ideal wife and not someone ‘useless’ and ‘unfit’ for work through *Banhi*.

The year 1927 saw the publication of Assam’s first women’s journal *Ghar-Jeuti* by the Sibsagar Mahila Samiti and edited by two women, Kanaklata Chaliha and Kamalalaya Chaliha. It provided a platform for the women to present their voice and also reflected the participation of Assamese women in the political and social movements of the time. No doubt it performed the role of mouthpiece for Assam Mahila Samiti, but no one can deny its distinct identity as a woman’s magazine. Its main objective was to bring the women of Assam together to initiate an effective education for them and ensure their development. *Ghar-Jeuti* paved the way for many emerging women writers and a few of them went to become well-known like Nalinibala Devi and Alaka Patangia. It also kept abreast the Assamese women about the happenings around the world and also about women in other countries. What is noteworthy is to come across the diverse views by the contributors regarding women’s education. The contradictions of the nationalist view on women’s role at that time are also evident in writers like Chandraprova Das, Punyaprova Das, Durbasundari Gogoi and Dipeswari Gohain. While talking about the women in the villages and asserting that women should be educated to assist the men folk Dipeswari Gohain makes a point that apart from reading and writing the women in the towns do nothing when compared to the village women (334-338). There were also writers like Labanyaprova Borbora who supported women’s education and their visibility

outside their homes for a better society, but noted at the same time that education for boys and girls should be different (623-627).

These journals provide us an insight into the contemporary attitude of the colonized in Assam which need to be deliberated upon in order to understand the status of the colonial women. The dire need and struggles for emancipation of women can be traced in these writings; the intelligentsia of colonial Assam had mixed feelings, but the fact that women took to writing is a proof enough of their repressed desires for equality. The reminder is always there that the Assamese women yearned for respect and freedom. Gillian Beer argues in her essay “Re-presenting Women: Re-presenting the Past” that, “Things mean differently at different historical moments, and different things need to be asserted at different times” (83). Beauvoir asserts in her *The Second Sex*: “She (woman) is defined and differentiated with reference to man and not he with reference to her; she is the incidental, the inessential as opposed to the essential. He is the Subject, he is the Absolute — she is the Other” (xvi). Women who did not conform to the norms dictated by the society were kept out of the scenario for being different and deviant. At the same time, we also find those who negotiated their way to establish their identity. Their deviant behavior is a trend and cultural response that cannot be ignored or overlooked.

When Edward Said said, “Orientalism failed to identify with human experience, failed also to see it as human experience”, he saw the silencing of the Orient by the Westerners in order to gain power over them. Similar is the Indian experience: “while Orientalism failed to identify with human experience, the many Indian texts today represent personal narratives, challenges to the hegemony of Orientalism, thus giving “voice” to human experiences of the Indian people, “speaking voices” of abjection, trauma, history, and (dis)assimilation (Gardner5). But today, when we see the plethora of Indian writers gaining popularity worldwide, we can say, people want to listen to that silence. And this has been achieved by the contemporary postcolonial writers that include the regional writers, too. Interrogation and historicizing of silence has brought to the fore the “speaking voices” which were hitherto being ignored. Barbara J. Gardner identifies “four types of “speaking voices”: abjection, magic realism, (dis)assimilation, and, since much of postcolonial writing deals with absences and a loss of voice causing a loss of history for the colonized, of special importance is the recovery of lost history through a voice “speaking history” (4-5).

The *Orunodoi* (1836) undoubtedly remains a significant source of “lost history” while it paved the way for the emergence of women writers in Assam. The American Baptist women were the first contributors to this periodical who “broke the local taboo against women writing

and their example may have encouraged the Assamese women converts to make similar attempts” (Mahanta150). A tradition of writing that developed with *Orunodoi* is noted by Aparna Mahanta when she informs about a century-old link between the writers Kunti Carolyn Symon in *Orunodoi* to her grand-daughter Priscilla Symon who wrote a novel *Hajag Nixa (Wakeful Nights, 1954)* (152). Since then, women writers of the colonial period can be traced in the pages of periodicals like *Assam Bandhu*, *Jonaki* and *Ghar-Jeuti*, but to unearth and understand the colonial Assamese woman such writings are not enough. At such a juncture Nirupama Borgohain, Mamoni Roisom Goswami, Tilottama Misra and Anuradha Sarma Pujari came around to retrieve the almost forgotten colonial women through their respective biographical novels, *Abhiyatri (Pathfinder) (1993)*, *Theng Phakhri Tehsildaror Tamor Taruwal (The Copper Sword of Theng Phakhri Tehsildar) (2009)*, *Swarnalata (1991)*, and *Mereng (2010)*. The interrogation of history by the novels results in the recovery of the so far repressed chapters and arouses the reader to reconsider the hitherto given facts.

The concerned four novels are an exploration of how history is being “textualized” and the texts are being “historicized”. In “Historical Fictions and Postcolonial Representation: Reading Girish Karnad’s Tughlaq”, Aparna Dharwadkar views that

In colonial and postcolonial contexts, legitimized histories coexist and often collide with non-historiographic, overtly fictional forms of historical writing that perform complex epistemological and cultural functions and intervene significantly in the discourse of history. The two kinds of narratives are fundamentally intertextual, since a serious historical "fiction" both emerges from and returns to "history"; indeed, at one level they can be regarded as alternative forms of figural representation... At another level, though, historical fictions can work precisely to neutralize or to repudiate the figurations of institutional history and can serve as alternative sources of historical knowledge for audiences ideologically resistant to the dominant narratives. In post- colonial India, where the past now appears to be largely an orientalist (mis)construction, fictions involving history must inevitably draw attention to the inherited problems of historical representation, even as they re-present history and invest it with new (but not necessarily ideal) meanings (43-44).

Tilottama Misra’s *Swarnalata (1991)* is based on the life story of Swarnalata Barua. She has always been known as the daughter of Gunabhiram Barua, the precursor of women’s education in Assam, and the first Assamese girl to study in Bethune, Kolkata, at a tender age of seven. Caught in the cusp of tradition and modernity she becomes the signature image of the

colonial woman in Assam – tradition-bound and silent. Rarely do we look beyond the apparent ‘achievement’ of Swarnalata and re-consider her state of being caught in the web of ‘home’ and the ‘world’. This dichotomy of the ‘home’ and the ‘world’ has never always been able to contain the voices of agency and resistance attained by the colonial women. Meeta Deka quotes Amartya Sen from his lecture entitled ‘Reason before Identity’ delivered in the University of Oxford in 1998: “(T)raditional inequalities such as unequal treatment of women ... often survive by making respective identities, which may include subservient roles of the traditional underdog, matters for unquestioning acceptance, rather than reflective examination. But the unquestioned presumptions are merely unquestioned – not unquestionable” (Intro XXIII). In *Swarnalata* we are made to be aware of the fact that the colonial women were not silent but made silent by patriarchy. The other side of this silence can be read as the agency and resistance of the colonial woman as Cixous puts in her essay “Sorties” – “Throughout their deafening dumb history, they have lived in dreams, embodied but still deadly silent, in silences, in voiceless rebellions” (101).

Theng Phakhri Tehsildaror Tamor Toruwal (The Copper Sword of Theng Phakhri Tehsildar) (2009) and *Abhiyatri (Pathfinder)* (1993), in different ways, present the colonial Assamese woman’s voicing of her selfhood which was subdued and most of the time overwhelmed by the male voice. The fourth chapter thus is a study of the different voices of agency and resistance as explored in these novels by Mamoni Roisom Goswami and Nirupama Borgohain respectively. *Abhiyatri* provides impetus to a woman to be very vocal and self-reliant through the tumultuous life of Chandraprova. This makes a significant study of the colonial woman who rebelled and gained acceptance in the society because “Every woman has known the torture of beginning to speak aloud, heart beating as if to break, occasionally falling into loss of language, ground and language slipping out from under her, because for woman speaking – even just opening her mouth – in public is something rash, a transgression” (Cixous98). Unlike Swarnalata, Chandraprova is the fiery other whose voice gave her the power to establish her own identity in society. The otherwise silent image of the colonial woman was shattered to usher in the new woman who has a voice of her own. She came to the fore full throttle that no one could deny her presence but acknowledge her strong personality. On the contrary, *Theng Phakhri Tehsildaror Tamor Toruwal* presents the portrayal of the colonial woman who is again voiceless. This time she is not just a mute spectator but dignified and feared, very much like Dora who could not be ‘tamed’ by Freud as Cixous said in her “Sorties”. Theng Phakhri’s silence gives her the greatest power to gain control over her subjects as the *tehsildar*. In spite of being a loyal servant to the British rulers she never falters to stand

up to her duties and responsibilities for her nation when the call came. Her integrity needs to be reckoned to study the colonial woman in Assam.

In the twilight of the colonial period, we perceive a change of perceptions regarding women that ushered in a new era for women. There was a realization of women's consciousness and self-assertion traced brilliantly in *Mereng* (2010) by Anuradha Sarma Pujari. This aspect that dawned upon the colonial Assamese woman is the gist of the fifth chapter. The question of identity and the changing perceptions of women are studied in this chapter to complete the analysis of re-presentation of the women in colonial Assam. The integrity of the protagonist Indira Miri enables her to negotiate her way to establish her identity and be a part of the decision-making sphere. Her married life and her subsequent widowhood with the constant shadow of her father provide enough space to study the colonial woman in Assam who was on the crossroads of change.

Apart from them, we cannot ignore Arupa Patangia who has drawn a very powerful picture of the colonial Assamese woman through the fictional character of Binapani in *Ayananta (Dawn)* (1994). When we are first introduced to Binapani, the protagonist of the novel, she is a free, independent spirit oblivious of the workings of the society. She was admitted to the critical social fabric when she was sent to her grandfather Nanda Barua's place for her education. There she came to know about the position of women in society. When she was asked by her mother to touch her grandfather's feet she refused and looked at him. Nanda Barua found himself in an embarrassing situation as he felt a kind of threat to his authority. Throughout his life he had been used to the "drooping eyelids of respect and fear" (Patangia11) and on that day he was unable to stand those searching eyes of a nine-year-old. Nanda Barua's predicament is similar to that of a section of the colonial Assamese society who had reservations regarding women stepping out of their homes and shattering the idea of the Angel in the House. They shuddered at the thought of women transgressing the traditional roles and turn out to be "luxury-loving, idle, and unfit for household work and demanding servants, which would be beyond the means of most middle class Assamese" (Mahanta21). Women had to transgress the traditional roles imposed upon them and discover their individual selves. Virginia Woolf, in *To the Lighthouse*, has Cam who refuses to be like her mother, but makes her "experience vivid moments of triumph and certainly much promise as she develops her sense and perception of herself as a modern woman" (Shanon Forbes482). So, like Cam, we can see the emergence of Theng Phakhri, Swarnalata, Chandraprova and Mereng as modern women who are "independent, free-thinking, free-speaking, ambitious individual" (Forbes483).

While studying these texts we see that the authors as well as their characters never turn away from men to create a different world, a world devoid of men (Sarma181). Nevertheless, women emerge as individuals having their individual freedom (Sarma5). Theirs is a real story from real experience, a facet that intrigues Julie Stephens –

A distinguishing feature of contemporary feminist discourse is that it purports to speak about ‘real women. It claims to record ‘the direct experiences of women’, to understand ‘the reality of being a woman in an Indian village’, and to examine how ‘lower-class’ women in India really feel about ‘being women’. This emphasis on realness, this faith that the descriptions of the Indian woman it offers are unproblematic representations of the objective, separates feminism from other discourses dealing with the same subject. Feminist studies aims to present ‘a vital and living portrait’ of Indian women which supplants the mythic and idealized ‘Indian womanhood’ of the nationalists or the objectified ‘woman’ of orthodox anthropology. Yet, in a discourse so concerned with challenging the very process by which traditional ‘images’ of women are produced, it is ‘surprising to find feminist texts blind to their own image-making and laying claim to accurately portray ‘real’ Third World women (92).

Susie Tharu, in response to Julie Stephens, argues,

Stephens invokes the concept of representation/ideology as discursively produced, rejecting, as it were, the notion of ideology as an expression of class interest or representation merely as a reflection of reality. One of the reasons why such an approach seemed a major advance over earlier expressive and totalizing ways of thinking was that coupled with the idea of ‘relative autonomy’ it opened up the possibility of understanding the ideological as an articulation of complex, sometimes contradictory and unevenly determining practices. As a consequence, a theory of struggle within the ideological became possible. In Stephens’ analysis, however, the multi-accentuality of the sign, its plurality or over determination, is closed off and a kind of ‘structural causality’, tailor-made for caricature, established. For all practical purposes the domain of ideology is reduced to the domain of a monolithically conceived ‘dominant ideology’ (127).

As Mrinalini Sinha argues, the feminist “reconceptualization of historiography not only emphasises the conditions in which politics and identities emerge, but also draws attention to the writing of history itself as an interventionary practice that recreates the past for the present.

It therefore opens up new possibilities for conceptualizing the problem of locating the Indian woman...” (Sarkar and Sarkar 234)

Ample work on women, especially the colonial women, has been undertaken throughout the world today and India is nowhere left behind. In India, we come across mostly women writers who are relentlessly working for the retrieval of the colonial women like Tanika Sarkar, Kumkum Sangari, Lata Mani, Geraldine Forbes, Mrinalini Sinha, Uma Chakraborty, to name a few. But sadly, it has been seldom that these women writers have been studied or their protagonists, some of the exemplary women from Assam in their respective works been evaluated. Even in Assam writings on them are very few and are not sufficient enough to comprehend the actual picture. Whatever work has been done for the retrieval of the colonial women in Assam, one cannot deny the relentless efforts of Aparna Mahanta, Tilottama Misra, Dipti Sharma, Renu Debi and S. L. Baruah whose works provide at least an early understanding and a picture, if not a detailed analysis or interpretation. Aparna Mahanta’s *Journey of Assamese Women, 1836-1937* provides interesting details on women’s education in the 19th and early 20th centuries and also traces the women writers of the early 20th century. The book includes an elaborate chapter on Chandraprova Saikiani and the Assam Mahila Samity. It traces the role of Chandraprova Saikiani as the precursor of women’s movement in Assam. The apotheosis of Joymati Kunwari is another remarkable feature of the book along with an in-depth reading of *Ghar-Jeuti*, the first Assamese women’s magazine. The concluding chapter deals exclusively on the emergence of the woman writer in Assam and winds up in a positive note:

It is heartening therefore to see in the late 19th century and the early twentieth century, how Assamese women used their limited resources of education, leisure time, opportunities to make a space for themselves in the field of Assamese literature despite the indifference and even obstructions of society. (189).

Women’s role in the national struggle for freedom is traced in *Assamese Women in the Freedom Struggle* (1993) by Dipti Sharma. Renu Debi and S. L. Baruah have edited two books of seminar papers, *Women of Assam* (1994) and *Status of Women in Assam* (1992) respectively. There is also Meeta Deka’s *Women’s Agency and Social Change* (2013) that has devoted a few pages on colonial women in Assam. More recently, Hemjyoti Medhi’s *Gendered Publics: Chandraprova Saikiani and the Mahila Samitis in Colonial Assam* (2023) has come as a whiff of fresh air to rekindle the emphasis to explore more about the women in colonial Assam. Books in the Assamese language are limited with only a few writers like Preeti Boruah, Binita Dutta and Sandhya Devi. These contemporary writers have made significant exploration of

colonial Assamese women as transmitters of culture and bearers of change, thus offering an alternative perspective that challenges the traditional views of women's role and agency.

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